

Appendix Table 7. Iguana element percentages for selected structures.

Structures selected for Tables 2-7 include those with the highest numbers of specific taxa, as well as a range of building types.

	Q-72 hall	Q-95 temple	Q-162 temple	Q-54 hall	R-106	R-112 house
limb	12.9%	23.6%	26.5%	16.0%	2.0%	8.8%
metapodial/phalanges	0.2%	0.2%		0.3%		
pelvis	9.0%	5.7%	8.0%	10.3%	10.0%	5.9%
rib	4.8%	0.7%	10.5%	0.6%		
shoulder	2.6%	1.8%	2.6%	1.3%	2.0%	
skull	18.7%	17.0%	11.7%	26.6%	28.0%	33.8%
tarsal	0.2%	0.4%		0.6%		
upper limb	14.3%	15.7%	14.8%	23.7%	30.0%	20.6%
upper limb lower	6.3%	9.5%	7.7%	11.2%	14.0%	7.4%
vertebra	30.8%	25.4%	18.2%	9.3%	14.0%	23.5%